

Interocean patterns in sponge assemblage structure and function

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Abstract

Sponges are a major component of benthic ecosystems across the world that fulfill a number of important functional roles. However, despite their importance, there have been few attempts to compare sponge assemblage structure and function across large spatial scales. In this review, we examine commonalities and differences between shallow water (<100 m) sponges at bioregional (15 regions) and macroregional (tropical, Mediterranean, temperate, and polar) scales to provide a more comprehensive understanding of sponges. Patterns of sponge abundance (based on density and area occupied) were highly variable, with an average area occupied between ~ 3 and 30%. Sponges generally were found to occupy more space in the Mediterranean and polar regions, compared to temperate and tropical regions, although the reverse was true for sponge densities (numbers of patches m⁻²). The mean species richness per standardised sampling area was similar across all bioregions, except for a few locations that supported very high small-scale biodiversity concentrations. Encrusting growth forms were generally the dominant sponge morphology, with the exception of coral reefs in the Western Atlantic, where more upright forms dominated. There were strong consistencies in the standardised respiration, pumping and growth rates between different bioregions, and a general consistency in sponge-associated organisms. With respect to reproduction, there were no patterns in gametic development (hermaphroditism versus gonochorism), although temperate, tropical, and polar macroregions had an increasingly higher percentage of viviparous species, with viviparity being the sole gamete development mechanism reported for polar sponges. Reproductive timing was generally seasonal in temperate bioregions and continuous in tropical bioregions. We found little variation across locations in larval size and the dominant larval type was parenchymella. Many organisms were found to predate on sponges, with the diversity of sponge predators being much higher in tropical systems. While there is evidence to support a higher overall proportion of phototrophic species in the Indo-Pacific bioregions compared to the Western Atlantic, both regions also have large numbers of heterotrophic species. Sponges are strong spatial competitors and generally outcompete most other invertebrates for space, irrespective of bioregions. Even though the data is limited for many regions, our analyses demonstrate some clear differences between bioregions and at the macroregional scale. However, there are also many similarities in sponge assemblage structure and function at global scales, likely reflecting a combination of regional- and local-scale biological and physical processes affecting sponge assemblages, along with common ancestry.

Introduction:

With declines in environmental quality reported in marine systems across the world (Boyce et al. 2010; Estes et al. 2011; Ramírez et al. 2017; Breitburg et al. 2018), there is an increasing need to understand the structure and function of key ecosystem components at a range of spatial scales (Gaston 2000). While many ecological studies focus on small to medium spatial scales (10s-1000s m), it is important to interpret changes and impacts in the context of regional and global scale trends to ascertain relative rates of change and to prioritise areas for conservation. However, building a clear picture of the ecology of a specific site or region takes considerable resources and time (see Hughes et al. 2017), meaning researchers are often limited to working in only a relatively small number of study locations. This has the potential to lead to researcher bias with respect to how a particular system or component of a system might function and respond to environmental perturbations. While avoiding the potential for such bias, global-scale analyses provide an opportunity to explore large-scale patterns, similarities and differences between phyla, assemblages and communities, while providing a better understanding of potential organism responses to environmental stress and anthropogenic impacts.

Sponges are sessile suspension feeders and a major component of benthic communities throughout tropical, Mediterranean, temperate, and polar ecosystems (Bell et al. 2015). Sponges have many important functional roles, largely resulting from their ability to filter large quantities of water (Wulff 2006; Bell 2008). In processing water, sponges remove particulate (POM) and dissolved (DOM) organic matter, thereby creating a strong link between benthic and pelagic ecosystems (e.g. Reiswig 1971; Reiswig 1975; McMurray et al. 2017). This removal of POM and DOM can have a strong impact on water column picoplankton abundance (Perea-Blazquez et al. 2012). In addition, the recent identification of the so-called 'sponge loop', in which sponges utilise DOC and subsequently produce detritus that can be consumed by higher trophic levels, further highlights the importance of sponge-water column interactions (de Goeij et al. 2013). Sponges also form associations with a range of macro- and micro-organisms, with the latter thought to be important for sponge survival and persistence (Webster and Taylor 2012). Moreover, sponges are important spatial competitors that can occupy a significant amount of space in benthic environments. This range of important functional roles performed by sponges means that changes in their abundance may have wider ecosystem impacts.

The first global patterns of sponge diversity, based primarily on extensive species distribution records (van Soest et al. 2012), and more recently global patterns of sponge-associated microbial communities (Thomas et al. 2016), have become available. While the assessment of global sponge richness patterns identified clear differences with respect to the total number of species reported/described, these patterns were not consistent with general patterns reported for other species, particularly the trend for greater diversity in the tropics. However, this apparent contradiction is most likely a result of historical sampling bias (van Soest 2012). For the global assessment of sponge-associated microbial communities, there were no evident geographical patterns (noting only 81 of a total >8500 sponge species were considered), with Thomas et al. (2016) concluding that independent assembly and evolution in symbiont communities are likely to have occurred across the sponge phylum.

In addition to these recent studies, a number of earlier studies have considered differences in sponge ecology across large geographic scales (Wilkinson 1987; Cheshire and Wilkinson 1987; Rützler 2004; Bell and Carballo 2008; Wulff 2012), although most have been restricted to specific habitat types or coral reefs (but see Wulff 2012). Wilkinson (1987) was the first to consider biogeographic variation in sponge assemblages, comparing broad-scale differences between Caribbean reefs and the Great Barrier Reef (GBR). He reported an order of magnitude more in consumption of organic matter on Caribbean coral reefs than on the GBR, resulting in 5 to 6 times greater biomass in the Caribbean. Interestingly, Wilkinson (1987) also reported a lack of phototrophic sponges (those predominately

reliant on photosynthetic symbionts) in the Caribbean compared to the GBR, which he explained as being a result of the clearer water on the GBR. Subsequently, Wilkinson and Cheshire (1990) compared reefs in Belize (Caribbean) with those on the GBR, finding higher productivity in sponges from Belize, which was again attributed to the greater reliance of GBR sponges on phototrophy. Rützler (2004) was the first to consider the differences in major coral reef biogeographic provinces for sponge assemblages, focusing on three regions: Indo-West Pacific, West Atlantic and the Pacific Islands. This work however, focused predominately on the distribution of the research effort in these regions rather than the specific geographical variation in sponge assemblage structure. Bell and Carballo (2008) considered diversity and density-area relationships of sponges inhabiting the undersides of the boulders in the Northeastern Atlantic (temperate – Lough Hyne), Central Pacific (tropical – Palmyra Atoll), and Eastern Pacific (temperate – Mazatlán) and found surprisingly consistent patterns. Wulff (2006) reviewed the variation in the sponge ecological interactions (including competition and predation) of sponges, and specifically considered the biogeographic patterns in sponge predators. Furthermore, Wulff (2012) reviewed the influence of abiotic factors and ecological interactions on patterns of diversity and abundance in different habitats ranging from mangroves to rock walls and coral reefs, highlighting the importance of ecological interactions in driving sponge abundance and distribution patterns. Most recently, Carballo et al. (2019) compared coral reef sponge assemblages from Eastern Tropical Pacific reefs (ETP) with West Pacific (WP) and Caribbean (CR) coral reefs, which shared a number of similarities, including the domination of very few species and occurrence of many rare species. However, while massive sponges dominated on CR and WP reefs, small encrusting and boring/cryptic species dominated ETP reefs. For similar depths (1-6 m), CR and WPR reefs had 7 times more individuals per m², and 4-5 more species per m² than ETP reefs. These authors proposed that local and large-scale perturbations, rather than biological factors, are most likely to explain the low prevalence and characteristics of ETP sponge assemblages.

Despite these earlier studies aiming to explore generalities and differences in the drivers of sponge assemblage structure, there has yet to be a comprehensive review of the structure, traits and function of sponges across the world and within different bioregions and macroregions. While data is still limited for sponges from many biogeographical regions, in this study we compiled existing information on shallow water sponges (<100 m) inhabiting hard substratum environments from across the globe in order to characterise the 'nature' of sponge assemblages in different biogeographic regions. We considered commonalities and differences in key sponge ecological traits and functional roles. We defined the boundaries of our biogeographic regions by firstly outlining our tropical bioregions based on a modification of the classification scheme outlined by Burke et al. (2011). We then used the original Marine Ecoregions of the World shapefile (Spalding et al. 2007) to outline temperate and polar bioregions, and modified it to include additional biogeographical provinces (Figure 1). Sponge traits examined included abundance (multiple metrics), richness, morphological composition, growth, reproduction, pumping rates, and respiration (Table 1). Functional roles surveyed included associated macrofauna, predation, heterotrophy versus phototrophy, and competition. Sponge bioerosion has attracted considerable attention due to the possible resilience of bioeroding sponges to the effects of climate change and their high abundance on certain degraded coral reefs (e.g. Schönberg and Ortiz 2009; Carballo et al., 2013; Fang et al. 2013; Wisshak et al. 2013; Stubler et al. 2015; Chaves-Fonnegra et al. 2015). Considering the availability of several comprehensive review articles documenting sponge bioerosion across the globe (Schönberg 2008; Schönberg et al. 2017a, b), we did not include this functional role in our review. Furthermore, global patterns of sponge diseases have been only recently considered (Luter and Webster 2017), and therefore also excluded from our study.

Biogeographical regions and approach

We focused on 15 biogeographic regions (henceforth bioregions, see Figure 1), and then combined them into tropical, Mediterranean (including the Black Sea), temperate, and polar macroregions, to identify patterns of sponge traits and functional roles across the globe. However, while there were numerous studies for tropical, Mediterranean, and temperate ecosystems, there was a limited number of studies of polar sponges. For each trait/functional role, we used a combination of Web of Science (www.webofknowledge.com) and Elsevier's Scopus (www.scopus.com) searches with specific search terms (see each section for respective terms), followed by a second search on Elsevier's DataSearch (datasearch.elsevier.com) to retrieve quantitative data from online repositories. We then examined Google Scholar and grey literature sources to ensure inclusion of all relevant studies for a particular sponge trait/functional role. Reference lists of the obtained records were then examined to identify any missing studies. All references found for each trait/functional role can be found in the supplementary information, and the total numbers of studies considered for each trait/functional role for each bioregion can be found in Table 1. Unpublished data was also provided by the authors, and, in some cases, from other non-published data sources. Our searches included all studies published prior to July 2018 and only data for shallow water marine sponges (<100 m depth).

Macroregion	Bioregion	Traits									Functional roles			
		Abundance	% cover	Species / area	Richness	Morphology	Growth	Reproduction	Pumping rates	Respiration	Heterotrophy vs Phototrophy	Predators	Competition	Associated macrofauna
Tropical	Central Pacific	4	4	5	2	2	1	2	0	0	1	4	5	1
	Tropical West Atlantic	4	1	2	0	2	4	16	12	4	4	19	47	15
	Tropical East Atlantic	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Middle East	2	2	1	2	0	0	3	1	2	0	2	3	4
	Indian Ocean	0	4	0	0	2	0	1	0	0	1	2	7	3
	South East Asia	6	7	6	2	2	0	4	0	2	0	7	11	2
	Tropical Australia	4	2	5	0	2	1	8	1	6	4	2	9	1
Mediterranean	Mediterranean	1	4	5	1	1	15	32	2	3	0	8	8	6
Temperate	North Pacific	1	0	1	1	0	2	8	1	1	0	2	7	1
	South East Pacific	3	1	2	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	North Atlantic	5	0	2	2	5	2	0	5	7	0	6	12	4
	South Atlantic	3	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Temperate Australasia	2	6	3	2	1	8	6	0	2	1	3	5	2
Polar	Arctic	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	5	0
	Antarctica	1	2	3	1	0	8	1	0	1	0	7	1	1
Total		37	33	35	17	16	42	82	22	28	11	62	118	39

Table 1. Summary of the total number of studies/data sets considered for each bioregion/macroregion for different sponge traits and functional roles.

Figure 1. The biogeographic regions used in this study, modified from Spalding et al. (2007) and Burke et al. (2011).

Richness and abundance

We collated the quantitative information available for entire sponge assemblages, including sponge abundance (number of sponge patches m^{-2}), percentage cover (area occupied), and two measures for species richness: 1) total species richness found in the total area sampled standardised to a unit area (1 m^2), which was termed 'SR1'; and 2) mean number of species per m^{-2} generally based on quadrat sampling, termed 'SR2'. Search terms included 'sponge/Porifera', and 'assemblage', 'biomass', 'abundance', and 'cover'. Although biomass is considered a reliable indicator of sponge abundance (see Wulff 2012), it can be difficult to measure for entire sponge assemblages, particularly where thin encrusting species are dominant (see below). Furthermore, because only a small number of studies have reported sponge biomass and many of them also contained other measures of sponge abundance, biomass was excluded from the metrics to enable more widespread comparisons.

The searches yielded 126 studies, which were screened for suitability. First, studies of sponge assemblages from soft substrata including muddy shelf, seagrass meadows, inter-reef seabed and mangroves were excluded, thus focusing on hard-bottom substrata only. All data with no indication of sampling effort (e.g. size and number of photoquadrats, length of transects, sampled area, etc.) were not considered further, as we wanted all metrics to be scaled to a unit area (1 m^2) for SR1. Investigations focusing on only one or very few species were also excluded (unless those few species represented the entire sponge assemblage at that location), as these studies were generally unable to capture the total abundance and diversity of the assemblage.

For abundance, percentage cover and richness per unit area (SR1), 68 studies met the criteria. Summary statistics were calculated or extrapolated for each study and were taken over three depth intervals: 0–20 m (shallow, routinely sampled with SCUBA), 20–40 m (mid-water, less commonly sampled with SCUBA), and 40–100 m (mesophotic, very rarely sampled with SCUBA). To examine general patterns of sponge metrics across tropical, Mediterranean, temperate, and polar macroregions, and within bioregions, we did not split the studies based on habitats as there were not enough studies within different habitat types to allow meaningful comparisons. Whenever mean values of sponge abundance, percentage cover, and richness per unit area were provided in a study, these values and their measure of uncertainty were used as summary statistics for that study. When, within a study a range of values was provided (for example, mean values from different sites, years, or species), summary statistics were calculated to best summarize the data that the study provided, capturing the within-study variability. When available, raw data were used to calculate mean values and standard deviations (SD). Where no raw data were provided or sample size was unknown, summary statistics were calculated for each study as a mean of the sample means and estimated SD (i.e. unweighted SD of the sample means). In all cases, SD was used to calculate the standard error of the mean (SE), since uncertainty was expressed as SE in the majority of the studies. When no numeric information was provided in a study and a graphical representation of the metrics of interest was the only available information, mean values and within-study variability were visually estimated from figures.

Of the 68 studies reporting quantitative information for entire sponge assemblages, 37 contained data on sponge abundance, 33 on percentage cover and 35 on species richness for a given total sampling area (SR1). Tropical bioregions had the most information available (35 studies), followed by temperate (24 studies), Mediterranean (7 studies), and polar bioregions (5 studies). Due to the between-study and between-bioregion variability in sampling techniques, median values of the metrics per bioregion were preferred over mean values for qualitative inter-bioregional comparisons (Figure 2). Of the 71 studies, only 13 contained information for habitats deeper than 20 m. Values reported hereafter will refer to median values as a descriptor of the metrics for each bioregion. Of the studies considered, 17

reported mean species richness per m^2 , which included extensive data from the authors. We did not separate this data into bioregions, but represented the information individually from the study areas, highlighting those from tropical, Mediterranean, temperate, and polar macroregions (Figure 3).

Of the tropical bioregions, shallow reefs in South East Asia had the highest median values of sponge abundance and percentage cover (50 sponges m^{-2} and 12%, respectively), and an SR1 of 1.5 species m^{-2} . Percentage cover was however highly variable between studies. Fewer studies were available for the Indian Ocean and Middle East than for other tropical regions, but in general these two bioregions reported the lowest sponge abundance and percentage cover. The Central Pacific was characterized by sponge cover of $\sim 3\%$ on shallow reefs, and by an SR1 of ~ 3.5 species m^{-2} . However, SR1 in this bioregion showed high variability, likely because of the spatial heterogeneity of the studied reefs. Both Western Atlantic and Tropical Australia had low reported values of sponge abundance, percentage cover and richness, with low variability between studies.

Shallow sponge assemblages in the Mediterranean region were characterized by high sponge percentage cover (median $\sim 28\%$), and the Mediterranean was the bioregion with the most studies deeper than 20 m. Mesophotic Mediterranean sponge assemblages were characterized by high species richness (median SR1 5.8 species m^{-2} at 20–40 m) and high percentage cover (but from a single study, $46.67 \pm 18.28\%$ at 40–100 m; mean and SE from Bo et al. 2011).

Temperate bioregions showed high variability of sponge abundance, cover and SR1. Shallow rocky reefs in temperate Australasia were characterized by the highest sponge abundance of all bioregions (median ~ 250 sponges m^{-2}) and a median percentage cover of $\sim 13\%$. The Eastern Pacific reported low values of abundance and species richness (SR1) compared to other bioregions. The North Atlantic showed median values of sponge abundance of ~ 76 sponges m^{-2} on shallow reefs, but reached mean values of $\sim 226 \pm 18.5$ sponges m^{-2} at Skomer in the United Kingdom (mean and SE from Berman et al. 2013). The North Atlantic was also characterized by relatively high SR1.

Polar studies were underrepresented in the literature, with those data available for entire assemblages showing high abundance and SR1 (Figure 2).

We collated data on the mean species richness (per m^{-2}) based on quadrat data (SR2) from 17 different locations covering tropical, Mediterranean, temperate, and polar locations (Figure 3). These data were provided both from the authors (unpublished data) and from the literature, but given the low number of overall studies, we presented all the data available in Figure 3. There was surprisingly similar mean species richness between tropical, temperate and polar regions, although data from multiple sites in Indonesia, that are separated by less than 2 km, showed highly variable species richness. The two highest mean species richness values were reported from a temperate (Skomer Island, United Kingdom) and a tropical site (Hoga Island, Indonesia), and, although tropical areas may have a higher overall total number of species, some temperate sites at small spatial scales had higher sponge richness.

Figure 2. Abundance, percentage cover and total species per unit area (species/area; SR1) standardised to a unit area (1 m²) at different depth ranges for all bioregions. Colours indicate the macroregion (i.e. tropical, Mediterranean, temperate, and polar). No data were available for the Tropical East Atlantic bioregion. Species/area included any study that reported a number of recorded taxa and a unit area and was calculated as number of taxa/area (SR1). Numbers near the boxes indicate the number of studies used to calculate the metric for that bioregion at that depth.

Figure 3. The mean species richness per m⁻² (SR2) based on quadrat data from 17 different locations covering tropical, Mediterranean, temperate, and polar locations. Vertical bars indicate SE as reported by the authors of each study. Note: data is both from the literature and collected by the authors.

Morphological variation

Sponge morphological diversity can be highly complex and variable (Boury-Esnault and Rützler 1997), and this variation has often been attributed to differences in environmental conditions (e.g. Barnes and Bell 2002). Search terms for this section included 'sponge/Porifera', and 'morphology', 'form', 'morphological variation', and 'shape'. We also included unpublished data collected by the authors, and data collected by Dr David Barnes (British Antarctic Survey), which provided comparable morphological assemblage data (similar sampling areas and units) from 27 locations representing 11 bioregions (Figure 4) that spanned tropical, Mediterranean, temperate, and polar locations. No data were available for the following bioregions: Arctic, North Pacific, South East Pacific and Tropical East Atlantic, and there was only one data point for the South Atlantic bioregion. Methods for calculating the abundance of different morphologies varied between studies, with some based on percentage cover data, one study on photogrammetric classification (Lawler and Osborn 2008), and one study on volume (Wulff 2006). To make the data comparable, we determined the prevalence of morphologies as a percentage of the total sponges observed, irrespective of the method used to estimate sponge abundance. Due to different morphological classification schemes used between studies, we aggregated sponges into the following major morphological groups: encrusting/cushion, branching/tubular/upright, massive, and bioeroding forms (see Bell et al. 2007).

Of the 27 studies considered, 14 were from the tropical bioregions, 2 were from the Mediterranean (no Black Sea data), 8 were from temperate bioregions, and 3 from polar bioregions. Encrusting sponges were the dominant morphology across all bioregions (Figure 5), representing over 50% of total morphologies observed. Massive sponges were the second most commonly observed morphological group (25%), with the exception of tropical regions, where massive and branching/upright forms were the second most common morphologies (22.3%). Bioeroding sponges

represented only a small proportion of the overall morphologies reported (1.8%), with an increasingly higher proportion reported in tropical, temperate and Mediterranean regions, respectively.

In all tropical bioregions, with the exception of the Tropical West Atlantic, low profile encrusting forms were the dominant sponge morphology (42.3 to 87.2%). However, there was no trend for the next dominant morphology, as upright forms were the second most dominant in some regions, while massive sponges were more dominant in others. In the West Atlantic region, which includes the Caribbean, upright and massive forms dominated (65.5 and 20.5%, respectively). In Panama, Wulff (2006) found that upright morphologies dominated (76.2%) at the start of a 14-year study (data extracted from Table 1), supported by Maldonado et al. (2017) (data extracted from Table 1) and our own data from Curaçao. There are only two relevant studies on sponge morphology of entire sponge assemblages in the South East Asia bioregion (Bell 2007; Hadi et al. 2015). Bell (2007) found sponge assemblages in South-East Sulawesi (Wakatobi National Park) are mostly encrusting species (77.2%), followed by massive forms (13.1%). In contrast, Hadi et al. (2015) reported dominance of massive sponge species (53%) followed by branching/tubular species (34.8%) in Lembah Strait, North Sulawesi. Combined observations from these two studies however, show that encrusting sponges are dominant in this bioregion, followed by massive and upright sponges. There was only one data point from the Indian Ocean bioregion represented by three locations along the east coast of Africa (Barnes and Bell 2002; 130 sponge species). The study reported that over 50% of the sponges occurring at these locations (Kenya, Mozambique and Madagascar) were encrusting, followed by massive (17.7%) and upright forms (11.7%). Morphological data from the Tropical Australia bioregion were obtained from two published studies (Wilkinson and Cheshire 1989; Farnham and Bell 2018, GBR and Timor Leste, respectively). Combined data from these studies showed that 63% of sponges in this region were encrusting species, followed by upright forms (29.1%). Representing the Central Pacific, data from Easter Island and Palmyra Atoll (authors unpublished data) indicated that sponges from that bioregion are mostly encrusting (73.7%) followed by massive (13.2%) and upright species (7.9%). Our single observation from the Middle East bioregion (Red Sea; across three local sites; authors' data) showed that sponges tended to exhibit mostly encrusting forms (50%) followed by massive (43%) and upright forms (4%).

We found only one published study reporting the morphological composition of an entire sponge assemblage from the Mediterranean. Gerovasileiou and Voultsiadou (2016) described the morphological diversity of 50 cave sponge species and found that encrusting sponges represented the most dominant morphology (71.9%) followed by massive (24.6%) and boring species (1.2%), although cave assemblages might not be representative of other benthic environments.

There were variable patterns in the abundance of different morphologies in temperate regions, but high proportions of encrusting sponges (>60%) generally dominated benthic communities. A total of eight studies were found for temperate regions, and sponge morphological diversity has been most heavily studied in the North Atlantic bioregion (5 studies), although all studies from this bioregion originate from only two locations (Skomer Island and Lough Hyne). From the combined studies of Bell and Barnes (2000) and Bell et al. (2006), the morphology of approximately 140 sponge species from these locations has been described. Bell and Barnes (2000) initially assessed the influences of bathymetry and flow regime on sublittoral sponge morphologies whereby they reported a high diversity of encrusting (57%) and massive (24.7%) forms in Lough Hyne. Berman et al. (2013) also reported high proportions of encrusting species (59%) at Skomer Island in South Wales. Four studies were found for the temperate Australasia bioregion including our own observations from around New Zealand (unpublished data) and the study of Lawler and Osborn (2008) that reported 232 sponge photogrammetric observations from Tasmania, Australia. Combining all datasets from this bioregion,

we found that sponges in Temperate Australasia are characterized primarily by encrusting species (57.6%) followed by upright (21.2%) and then massive (21%) species. Information for the North Pacific bioregion was available from Carballo and Nava (2007), which again showed sponge assemblages dominated by mostly encrusting (87.2%), followed by massive (8.5%) and then upright forms (4.3%).

Sponge morphologies for entire sponge assemblages in polar regions is relatively unknown, with no morphological data reported from the Arctic bioregion. Polar sponge assemblages, represented by data from three sites in the Antarctic (South Georgia, Falkland Island and Ushuaia; data from David Barnes) showed that this bioregion is dominated by encrusting species (72.1%), followed by massive species (21.8%), and low proportions of upright species (6.1%).

Figure 4. Variation in the proportion of different major morphological groups across tropical, Mediterranean, temperate, and polar macroregions. Numbers along the y-axis represent the number of data points used to create the estimates.

Figure 5. Variation in the proportion of different major sponge morphological groups across 12 bioregions. The numbers in parentheses show the number of data points from which the proportions are derived.

Associated organisms

Sponge-associated microbes have been well-studied and are the subject of a number of reviews (e.g. Thomas et al. 2016); consequently, here we have focused only on sponge-associated macrofauna. Specific search terms for this section included: 'sponge/Porifera', and 'associated organisms', 'macrofauna', 'associated fauna', 'endofauna', and 'epifauna'. Research on sponge-associated macrofauna has been conducted using a variety of methods including *in situ* identification, scraping fauna from the outside surface of the sponge, filtration through sieves of different sizes, sponge dissection, visual searches, stereomicroscopy, histology and scanning electron microscopy (SEM). Generally, we found that the density of fauna and number of species was more dependent on both the method used and sponge species identity rather than the geographic location. In addition, several studies were very specific, focusing on one taxonomic group of associated organisms or on very few sponge species. Therefore, we summarized mostly phylum-, class-, and order-level taxonomic groups of fauna associated with sponges in each bioregion. In total we found 25 tropical, 6 Mediterranean, 7 temperate, and 1 polar studies (see Table 2 for summary).

A diverse macrofaunal community has been found to be associated with sponges in tropical environments (Table 2). The Tropical West Atlantic was the most studied bioregion (15 of the 25 tropical studies). However, many tropical studies were narrow in scope. For example, the only study conducted in the Central Pacific focused only on Polychaeta (Lopez et al. 2001), and the only study in Tropical Australia, focused on endofauna rather than the total macrofaunal community (Skilleter et al. 2005). The two studies for South East Asia focused on only Polychaeta and barnacles (Magnino et al. 1999a; Sarda et al. 2002). Two additional studies in tropical environments focused only on Polychaeta (Dauer 1973; Magnino and Gaino 1998), three only on synalpheus shrimp (Erdman and Blake 1987; Duffy 1992; MacDonald et al. 2009), one each on barnacles (Ilan et al. 1999), Ophiuroidea (Henkel and Pawlik 2005), and Amphipoda (Serejo 1998), and another two on endofauna (Westinga and Hoetjes 1981; Duarte and Nalesso 1996). The single study in Tropical Australia was limited to endofauna, where few taxonomic groups were reported (Polychaeta, Tanaidacea, Isopoda, Hexanauplia, and Nematoda). The three bioregions that have more analyses of macrofauna are the Indian Ocean, Middle East and the Tropical West Atlantic, which have reported a much higher diversity of macrofauna compared to other regions. All three bioregions found Polychaeta, Sipuncula, Bivalvia and Gastropoda, Ophiuroidea, several crustaceans (Tanaidacea, Amphipoda, Decapoda, Hexanauplia), and Cnidaria. The Indian Ocean and Tropical West Atlantic both reported Nematoda, while the Middle East and Tropical West Atlantic studies reported Platyhelminthes, Nemertea, Isopoda, Ostracoda, Chordata, and Echinoidea. Polyplacophora and Mysida have only been reported from the Indian Ocean. Bryozoa, Foraminifera, Ascidiacea, Holothuroidea, Arachnida, and Pycnogonida have been reported exclusively from the Tropical West Atlantic. No relevant studies were found from the Tropical East Atlantic bioregion.

For the Mediterranean, two studies focused only on Polychaeta (Cinar and Ergen 1998; Gherardi et al. 2001), while another four studies reported a wider range of macrofauna including Annelida, Arthropoda, Chordata, Cnidaria, Echinodermata, Mollusca, Platyhelminthes, and Sipuncula (Voultsiadou-Koukoura et al. 1987; Koukouras et al. 1992; Koukouras et al. 1996; Cinar et al. 2002).

For temperate bioregions, no studies were found from the South Atlantic and South East Pacific bioregions, and only one study was from the North Pacific (Long 1967). Two studies focused only on amphipods (Costello and Myers 1987; Poore et al. 2000), and one on endofauna rather than the total macrofauna community (Abdo 2007). Macrofauna found associated with sponges in temperate

bioregions was diverse (Table 2). Sponge associates including Polychaeta, Amphipoda and Decapoda, and Bivalvia and Gastropoda (or general Mollusca) were found in all three temperate bioregions with available information. Ophiuroidea were found in the North Atlantic, North East Pacific, and Temperate Australasia, and Isopoda, Nematoda, and Chordata were found in both the North Atlantic and Temperate Australasia bioregions. Pycnogonida have only been reported from the North Atlantic, Bryozoa and Hydrozoa only from the Northeast Pacific, and Crinoidea only from Temperate Australasia.

Only one study reported information from polar bioregions that matched our criteria for sponge-associated fauna, and this was from Antarctica (Amsler et al. 2009). This article reported that high amphipod numbers are associated with several sponge species in the Antarctic. However, the limited literature from this region (particularly from <100 m depth) makes it difficult to determine the extent of sponge-macrofauna associations. No studies were found for associated macrofauna for Arctic sponges.

Growth

Measuring sponge growth can be difficult due to complex external morphology and internal architecture, and as a result of the lack of measurable features present in other organisms (e.g. otoliths in fish; Mercier et al. 2011). While variation among species is likely due to differences in morphologies, previous work on sponges has described highly variable growth among sponges, possibly due to a difference in 'individual' fitness in the face of environmental variability (De Caralt et al. 2008). Using the search terms 'sponge/Porifera', and 'growth' and 'size change', 62 studies were identified as measuring growth in sponges. The literature contained 3 dominant growth indicators: percentage growth (increase/decrease in size as a percentage of the original size; n=42), growth rate (increase in volume/size standardised over unit time; n=12), and specific growth rate (final size minus initial size standardised over unit time; n=8). We focused only on percentage growth as it had the highest number of studies. The mean percentage growth rate was standardised from published values to percentage growth per day (mean growth rate (%) day⁻¹). Given some studies measured percentage growth under experimental conditions, we only considered results for 'control' sponges in these studies to represent as natural rates as possible (noting that rates may have been influenced by being in an experimental system).

Variability in sponge growth is well reported in the literature; in some cases growth is seasonal (Leys and Lauzon 1998; Turon et al 1998; Garrabou and Zabala 2001), whereas in other species growth measurements are confounded by shrinkage (Turon et al. 1998; Garrabou and Zabala 2001). Previous studies have shown that sponge growth trends vary with environmental quality, though most of this research has emphasized the seasonal effects of temperature (Leys and Lauzon 1998; Turon et al. 1998; Garrabou and Zabala 2001; McMurray et al. 2008). Mean growth rate (%) day⁻¹ varied at the macroregional scale, but appeared relatively similar across all individual bioregions (data not shown). Comparing temperate, tropical, Mediterranean, and polar regions (Figure 6) showed some evidence of an overall increase in growth, respectively. The mean values of percentage growth rate day⁻¹ (\pm SE) per macroregion, followed by the number of studies and species included (in brackets) are as follows: polar (0.072 ± 0.019 ; n = 1 [3]), temperate (0.189 ± 0.099 , n = 6 [8]), Mediterranean (0.295 ± 0.092 , n = 5 [11]), and tropical (0.361 ± 0.199 , n = 5 [7]).

Figure 6. Boxplot representing the median of the mean percentage growth rate day⁻¹ for sponges from tropical, Mediterranean, temperate, and polar. Numbers on the boxplots show the number of data points used to estimate the medians.

Reproduction I: mode, gamete development and synchrony

Sponges reproduce both sexually and asexually (as reviewed in Maldonado and Riesgo 2009). For sexual reproduction, sponges can either be gonochoristic, hermaphroditic, or both; and with respect to gamete development, either release eggs into the water column (oviparous), internally brood larvae (viviparous), or internally develop eggs that hatch (ovoviviparous). Asexual reproduction occurs through three mechanisms: budding, fragmentation, and gemmulation (Simpson and Gilbert 1973; Maldonado and Uriz 1999; Cardone et al. 2010). The frequency of recruitment may occur in short discrete periods or continuously throughout the year (e.g. Ayling 1980; Wahab et al. 2014a; 2014b; 2014c). To assess global patterns, we recorded three main qualitative characteristics for each sponge species where data were available: 1) gamete production (hermaphroditism, gonochorism, or both), 2) gamete development (oviparous, viviparous, or ovoviviparous); and 3) frequency of reproductive events (seasonal or continuous). For asexual reproduction, the type of asexual reproduction (budding, fragmentation, or gemmulation) was also recorded. Search terms included 'sponge/Porifera', and 'sexual reproduction', 'asexual reproduction', 'gamete', and 'gametic development', which yielded 82 studies. Only 4 bioregions (Mediterranean, Temperate Australasia, Tropical Australia, and Tropical West Atlantic) had more than one study discussing mechanisms for asexual reproduction, and therefore other bioregions were not considered for this aspect of reproduction.

There were 62 studies from tropical bioregions (Figures 7–9), but there were no studies from the Tropical East Atlantic and only two studies describing reproduction in the Central Pacific. These studies examined two sponge species, and found that *Thoosa mismalolli* was a continuous, hermaphroditic, and viviparous reproducer (Bautista-Guerrero et al. 2010), while *Cliona vermifera* was a seasonal, gonochoristic, and oviparous reproducer (Bautista-Guerrero et al. 2014). There was only one study from the Indian Ocean, focusing solely on asexual reproduction (Singh and Thakur 2018), although it seems likely sexual reproduction does occur here. These authors reported asexual budding events for *Cinachyrella* cf. *cavernosa*, which had seasonal asexual reproductive events. The studies relating to reproduction in the Middle East bioregion were only from the Red Sea and examined sexual reproduction in eight species. These species exhibited strictly seasonal reproduction, and were mostly hermaphroditic and viviparous (Ilan and Loya 1990; Meroz and Ilan 1995; Ilan et al. 2004). Asexual reproduction has only been recorded for one species to date in this bioregion, where *Amphimedon chloros* was found to undergo fragmentation (Ilan et al. 2004). Reproduction in South East Asia has been characterized for four species, with all exhibiting viviparity and seasonal reproduction (Asa et al. 2000; Chung et al. 2010; Nozawa et al. 2016; Huang et al. 2016). Hermaphroditism was the prominent mode of gamete development in this region, found for 75% of species. Furthermore, only one instance of asexual reproduction has been recorded for this bioregion, which is fragmentation in *Terpios hoshinota* (Nozawa et al. 2016). Reproduction for sponges in Tropical Australia has been characterized solely on the GBR, with eight studies looking at reproduction in eleven different species (e.g. Fromont 1994; Whalan et al. 2007a; 2007b; Wahab et al. 2014c, 2017). This region is characterized mainly by continuous sexual reproduction (91% of observed species), and more than two thirds of the species that have been studied in the GBR are gonochoristic and oviparous. Fragmentation is the only mode of asexual reproduction recorded in this region to date. The Tropical West Atlantic region has the second most sponge reproduction studies (after the Mediterranean), with 16 studies examining sexual and asexual reproduction in 31 species and 66% of the information coming from the Caribbean (e.g. Hoppe 1988; Kaye and Reiswig 1991; Leong and Pawlik 2011). This bioregion is characterized by diverse reproductive traits. Instances of seasonal sexual reproduction, gonochorism, and viviparity are slightly more common, each being recorded for more than 60% of species. All three mechanisms of asexual reproduction (e.g. budding, fragmentation, and gemmulation) have been recorded in this bioregion, with fragmentation being the most common (Figure 9).

The majority of studies relating to sponge reproduction originated from the Mediterranean bioregion. Here, reproductive traits have been detailed for nearly 40 species (e.g. Uriz and Maldonado 1999; Riesgo and Maldonado 2008; Gaino et al. 2010; de Caralt and Cebrian 2013; Ereskovsky et al. 2013), and a variety of sexual reproductive patterns and strategies have been recorded. There was no dominant pattern for timing, gamete production or gamete development in the Mediterranean (Figure 7). However, for reproductive timing, 72% of species were seasonal reproducers. Oviparity and gonochorism were slightly more common (>50% of species), while ovoviviparous species have only been recorded in the Mediterranean region. Budding is the main asexual reproduction mechanism recorded in the Mediterranean.

For temperate bioregions, reproduction has been characterized for six species in the Temperate North Atlantic bioregion (Chen et al. 1976; Barthel et al. 1986; Witte et al. 1994; Stephens et al. 2013; Stubler et al. 2017). All these species exhibited seasonal reproduction, and gonochorism and viviparity were recorded most frequently in this region (60% and 75% of observed species, respectively). There are no published descriptions of asexual reproduction in the Temperate North Atlantic, although at least one species of *Tethya* is known to produce buds (Bell unpublished data). There are three studies on sexual reproduction from the North Pacific (Elvin 1976; Amano 1988; Carballo and Avila 2004). Seasonal reproduction, viviparity and instances of both hermaphroditism and gonochorism were

recorded for the sponges from this bioregion. Temperate Australasia was characterized by sponges that are generally gonochoristic and are seasonal sexual reproducers (Ayling 1980; Usher et al. 2004; Whalan et al. 2007a; Abdo et al. 2007; Roberts et al. 2006; Shaffer 2019). About half of the 15 species that have been studied to date exhibit oviparity, while the other half internally brood their larvae. Asexual reproduction, exclusively through budding, has also been recorded for one-third of these species, (Ayling 1980; Shaffer 2019). There were no studies to date examining reproduction in the South Atlantic or South East Pacific bioregions.

There have only been two studies examining reproduction in polar bioregions, one in each of the Arctic and Antarctic. The study examining sexual reproduction in the Antarctic characterized reproduction for six sponge species (Koutsouveli et al. 2018). Only information on gamete development was described, and all six species were found to be viviparous. The only study examining sexual reproduction in the Arctic (Ereskovsky 2000) examined three species, all of which exhibited seasonal sexual reproduction and viviparity. Two of the species were identified as hermaphroditic.

Figure 7. Qualitative reproductive characteristics for sponges in the 15 bioregions. a) Percentage of species that are hermaphroditic, gonochoristic, or both. b) Percentage of species that are viviparous, oviparous, or ovoviviparous. c) Percentage of species exhibiting seasonal versus continuous sexual reproduction. Numbers along the y-axis represent the number of species considered for each bioregion. The symbol “X” indicates no information is currently available in the literature for that bioregion.

Figure 8. Qualitative sexual reproductive characteristics for sponges in tropical, Mediterranean, temperate, and polar bioregions. a) Percentage of species that are hermaphroditic, gonochoristic, or both. b) Percentage of species that are viviparous, oviparous, or ovoviviparous. c) Percentage of species exhibiting seasonal versus continuous sexual reproduction. Numbers along the y-axis represent the number of species considered for each bioregion.

Figure 9. Mechanisms of asexual reproduction for sponges in 4 bioregions. Numbers along the y-axis represent the number of species considered for each bioregion.

Reproduction II: larval size and type

In this section, data were collated for bioregion variation in: 1) larval type; and 2) larvae size (μm). Search terms included 'sponge/Porifera', and 'larvae' and 'larval morphology', 'reproduction', and 'ontogenetic stage'. The searches yielded 70 studies containing information on at least one of the topics. Of these studies, 51 were selected based on comparability and presence of quantitative and descriptive data. Studies that provided only descriptive information but failed to present specific or comparable data were excluded. All data with no indication of sampling effort (e.g. size and type, method of observation, sampled area, etc.) were not considered further, to ensure all metrics were standardised to the same unit of time or space (size- μm).

Of the 51 studies analysed, 36 contained data on larvae type and 31 on larvae size. Tropical bioregions and the Mediterranean had the most information available (22 and 16 studies, respectively), followed by temperate (8 studies) and polar bioregions (5 studies). Median values and boxplots of the size data from the studies are shown in Figure 10, and proportions of larval type by bioregion and macroregions are reported in Figure 11. Across all studies, 70% of the sponges had parenchymella larvae, with the most diversity of larval types being identified for sponges from temperate bioregions. There were differences in the proportion of different larval types reported between tropical, Mediterranean, temperate, and polar regions, but no clear trends found for larval size.

Figure 10. a) Proportion of different sponge larval types found in 15 different bioregions, and b) combined for tropical, Mediterranean, temperate, and polar macroregions. Numbers along the y-axis represent the number of species considered for each bioregion.

Figure 11. Size of larvae found in the 15 different bioregions. The numbers on the boxplots are the number of species on which the estimates are based.

Tropical studies accounted for over one-third of the total studies (22), with the majority from the Tropical Western Atlantic (7) and Tropical Australasia (8). The Indian Ocean bioregion lacked data regarding larvae ecology. In addition, only parenchymella larvae have been reported for South East Asia. Three studies reported information from the Central Pacific bioregion, which reported parenchymella larvae for *Callyspongia ramosa* (Amano 1988) and *Haliclona caerulea* (Avila and Carballo 2006), and hoplitomella larvae for *Thoosa mismalolli*. The coral excavating sponge, *Thoosa mismalolli*, revealed unique larval behaviour due to the radial spicules that stick out externally from its hoplitomella structure that potentially act as flotation devices or even paddles during dispersal, potentially enabling larvae to travel long distances (Bautista-Guerrero et al. 2010). Studies from the Middle East (Red Sea) only reported sponges (*Chalinula* sp. and *Niphates* sp.) producing parenchymella larvae. Tropical West Atlantic sponge assemblages were also dominated by species that produce parenchymella larvae (3 types: unspecified, tufted, and untufted), but also clavablastula and amphiblastula larvae. Tropical Australasia studies focused primarily on the GBR, where data were available for five species, all having parenchymella larvae.

The Mediterranean bioregion provided the most information regarding larval ecology, with over 30 species investigated in 16 separate studies. Two main larval types were found: cinctoblastula (Boury-Ensault et al. 2003) and parenchymella (unspecified, tufted, and non-tufted variety) (Mariani et al. 2006).

Temperate bioregions accounted for 8 of the studies identified, with 4 pertaining to Temperate Australasia, where the larvae observed were all coeloblastula and parenchymella larvae. Ten species have been studied in the North Atlantic and they all had parenchymella larvae (Fell et al. 1984;

Wapstra and Van Soest 1987). Larvae found in the North Pacific were restricted to relatively small parenchymella (unspecified and non-tufted structures) and one calcareous amphiblastula.

Only three different larvae morphologies have been reported for the Arctic: parenchymella, dipherula, and calciblastula. Information on the larval characteristics of Antarctic sponge species was limited, with only three studies identified. Only one sexual larvae type was reported for *Mycale acerata*, which produces non-tufted parenchymella larvae (Riesgo et al. 2015).

Respiration

We identified a total of 39 studies that have investigated respiration rates in shallow water marine sponges using the search terms 'sponge/Porifera', and 'respiration' and 'oxygen consumption'. There are three main ways of normalising oxygen consumption rates: O_2 g(dry weight)⁻¹; O_2 g(live weight)⁻¹, and O_2 ml(fresh weight)⁻¹, and we excluded those papers using other units, which left 28 studies. In addition, all the oxygen values expressed in $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$, nmol L^{-1} and ml L^{-1} were converted in mg L^{-1} to standardise between studies. No data were found from the following bioregions: Indian Ocean, Central Pacific, South East Pacific, South Atlantic, and Arctic. Where data were extracted from experimental studies, we only used information from control sponges.

Information on oxygen consumption rates were often available in more than one unit for the same sponge species, for example, Thomassen and Riisgårdin (1995) used all three units to measure respiration rates in *Halicondra panicea*; Ludeman et al. (2017) used both $\text{mg } O_2 \text{ g(dw)}^{-1}$ and $\text{mg } O_2 \text{ ml(fw)}^{-1}$ for six sponge species. Across the 28 studies, oxygen consumption rates have been measured in 51 sponge species worldwide (Figure 12), with respiration rates expressed in $\text{mg } O_2 \text{ g(dw)}^{-1} \text{ h}^{-1}$ in 13 studies (24 sponge species), in $\text{mg } O_2 \text{ ml (fw)}^{-1} \text{ h}^{-1}$ in 12 studies (30 sponge species), and in $\text{mg } O_2 \text{ g(fw)}^{-1} \text{ h}^{-1}$ in 9 studies (21 sponge species). Tropical bioregions had the most information available (14 studies representing 25 sponge species), followed by temperate bioregions (10 studies representing 19 species), Mediterranean (3 studies representing 2 species), and polar regions (1 study representing 4 species). Irrespective of the respiration measure used, there were no obvious trends between bioregions, with the possible exception that respiration rates were generally lowest for polar species and higher for temperate sponges, compared to other the macroregions, but only based on dry weights. However, this was only based on observations of four polar species (Figure 12).

Figure 12. Sponge oxygen consumption rates across 15 bioregions and for tropical, Mediterranean, temperate, and polar bioregions based on: a) sponge dry weight, b) volume and c) wet weight. The numbers on the boxplots represent the total number of observations for each bioregion and may contain multiple data for the same species.

Pumping rates

To assess the geographical variation in pumping rates, we used the search terms 'sponge/Porifera', and 'water flow', 'pumping', and 'osculum'. We identified 36 studies that have investigated pumping rates in shallow water marine sponges. The most commonly used unit for the normalisation of pumping rates is the overall sponge volume (ml), and we excluded those papers that used other units, which left 22 studies reporting data for 33 sponge species. As some of the pumping rates were expressed in different volume and time units, we converted the data to $\text{l h}^{-1} \text{ml}(\text{sponge})^{-1}$ to standardize between studies. No data were found from the following bioregions: Indian Ocean, Central Pacific, South East Asia, South Atlantic, South East Pacific, South Atlantic, Temperate Australasia, Arctic, and Antarctica. Tropical bioregions had the most information available (14 studies on 23 sponge species), followed by temperate bioregions (6 studies on 9 sponge species), and the Mediterranean (two studies on one sponge species). Overall, there were no obvious patterns between bioregions or macroregions (Figure 13), and often rates were highly variable even within a single species. For example, several authors have investigated pumping rates in the barrel sponge *Xetospongia muta*. Southwell et al. (2008), Weisz et al. (2008), and McMurray et al. (2014), found similar values ($\sim 0.2 \text{ l h}^{-1} \text{ml}(\text{sponge})^{-1}$), while Fiore et al. (2013) found much higher values for the same species ($0.432 \pm 0.468 \text{ l h}^{-1} \text{ml}(\text{sponge})^{-1}$).

Figure 13. Sponge pumping rates (standardised to $\text{l h}^{-1} \text{ml}(\text{sponge})^{-1}$) from 33 sponge species across 22 studies covering tropical, Mediterranean, temperate, and polar macroregions. The numbers on the boxplot represent the total number of observations used to create each box and may contain data for the same species but from different studies.

Predation

Wulff (2006) previously considered the ecological interactions between sponges and their predators and here we report the different sponge predators reported from the different macroregions. Search

terms for this section included terms 'sponge predator', 'sponge predation', 'spongivore', and 'sponge diet'. We identified 62 studies, 36, 8, 11, and 7 were from tropical, Mediterranean, temperate, and polar macroregions, respectively. To date there have been no studies of predation in Arctic sponges, but in Antarctica several studies have identified nudibranchs and starfish as the most important sponge predators (Dayton et al. 1974; Dayton et al. 1989; see McClintock 2005 for review) (Figure 14), with other predators including amphipods (Graeve et al. 2001; Amsler et al. 2009), brittle stars (Fratt and Dearborn 1984; see McClintock 1994 for review), nemertean (Dayton et al. 1989; Brueggeman 1998) and sub-Antarctic holothuroids (McClintock 1994).

A high diversity of sponge predators has been reported in tropical bioregions (see Wulff 2006 for full review), although fish have been the most reported (Figure 14). The Western Atlantic was the most well-researched bioregion for sponge predators, where one of the most well-known sponge-feeders in the region is the Hawksbill turtle, which has been documented to feed exclusively on a narrow range of available sponges (Meylan 1988). A range of fish species have been reported feeding on sponges as both specialist and inadvertent feeders. These include angelfish, filefish, boxfish, pufferfish, spadefish, parrotfish and triggerfish (Randall and Hartman 1968; Turingan et al. 1995; Dunlap and Pawlik 1998; Pereira et al. 2016). However, debate remains as to whether parrotfish should be characterised as spongivores since their exploitation of sponges is considered opportunistic rather than regular feeding (Wulff 2017). Generalist macro-invertebrate grazers have also been reported to consume sponges in the Western Atlantic, including starfish, urchins, brittle stars, polychaetes, and snapping shrimp (Reiswig 1973; Pawlik 1983; Wulff 1995; Santos et al. 2002; Henkel and Pawlik 2014). In the Central Pacific bioregion, there are also reports of spongivorous angelfish, filefish, pufferfish (Hiatt and Strasbourg 1960; Hobson 1974; Perez España and Abitia Cardenas 1996; Verdín Padilla et al. 2010), and some anecdotal evidence of parrotfish predation (Bakus 1967). In this bioregion, butterfly fish and Moorish Idols are also important predators (Hobson 1974). Sponge spicules have also been found in the faecal content of 5 of 23 species of nudibranchs and two species of fish on the Mexican Pacific coast on the border of the Central Pacific and North Pacific regions (Verdín Padilla et al. 2010). There was almost no information regarding spongivores in the Indian Ocean bioregion. In the only study, Ďuriš et al. (2011) found spongian fibres in the intestinal tract of the snapping shrimp *Synalpheus cf. hastilicrassus* collected from the Yemeni Island of Socotra (Ďuriš et al. 2011). Similar to the Indian Ocean region, references of sponge predators were limited for the Middle East bioregion. There were very few studies of sponge predators in Tropical Australasia with only reports of rabbitfish species regularly ingesting sponges as part of their diet at some ontogenetic stages (Pitt 1997; Hoey et al. 2013). Similar to the other tropical bioregions, sponge-feeding was a noted characteristic of angelfish in the South East Asian bioregion (Eagle and Jones, 2004; Powell et al. 2015), along with butterfly fish (Sano 1989; Naglekerkern et al. 2009). As in the Central Pacific, the Moorish Idol *Zanclus cornutus* has been observed actively removing sponge tissue on coral reefs in Indonesia (Powell et al. 2015). Invertebrate sponge predators documented in the South East Asia bioregion included shrimps (Ďuriš et al. 2011) and nudibranchs (Zhukova 2014; Powell et al. 2015).

A number of authors in the Mediterranean have identified crustaceans (Figure 14), including snapping shrimp (e.g. Rützler 1976; Ďuriš et al. 2011) and copepods (Mariani and Uriz 2001), along with nudibranchs (e.g. Becerro et al. 2003; Gemballa and Schermutzki 2004) as the main sponge predators in this bioregion. The only reported vertebrate predator of sponges in the Mediterranean that we identified is the loggerhead turtle *Caretta caretta* with 8.3% of the total overall gut contents of 79 individuals being identified as sponge (Casale et al. 2008).

Temperate sponge predators appeared to be more diverse (Figure 14) than those reported from the Mediterranean and included nudibranchs (Guida 1976; Bloom 1976; Knowlton and Highsmith 2000), microgastropods, urchins, limpets, isopods, (Guida 1976; Vance 1979), amphipods, snapping shrimp, starfish, crabs, fish (Guida 1976; Russel 1971; Ayling 1981; Sheild and Witman 1993; Wieczorek and Hooper 1995) and one observation of a predatory polychatete (Witman 1998). The North Atlantic bioregion was the most studied temperate bioregion. In the North Atlantic, Guida (1976) investigated predation on the boring sponge *Cliona celata* inhabiting oyster shells in North Carolina and found that six species frequently eat the exposed ventilation papillae of *C. celata* (gastropods, nudibranchs, urchins, limpets, isopods and a snapping shrimp). Other examples of micro-predators reported from the North Atlantic included amphipods (Oshel and Steele 1985), starfish (Sheild and Witman 1993) and a scavenging snow crab (Wieczorek and Hooper 1995). In the North Pacific, nudibranchs and urchins (Vance 1979; Birenheide et al. 1993; Knowlton and Highsmith 2000) have been reported to consume sponges. Fish predation on sponges has only been reported from the Temperate Australasian bioregion. In New Zealand, the filefish *Meuschenia scaber* has been found to have over 35% gut full of sponge (Russel 1971), which has been further supported by feeding observations of sponge grazing activities (Ayling 1981). The urchin *Evechinus chloroticus*, known locally as 'kina' in New Zealand, also consumes sponge as part of its diet (Ayling 1981), as do nudibranchs and potentially spiny lobsters (MacArthur et al. 2011).

Figure 14. The proportion of different sponge predators across tropical, Mediterranean, temperate, and polar macroregions. Numbers along the y-axis represent the total number of species found for each macroregion.

Phototrophy versus heterotrophy

To identify differences in the reliance of sponges on heterotrophy and autotrophy, we used the search terms 'sponge/Porifera', and 'feeding', 'heterotrophy', 'autotrophy', and 'photosynthesis'. While sponges harbour a wide diversity of microbes and other symbionts (Webster and Taylor 2012), there has been considerable interest in the role that photosynthetic symbionts play in contributing to

sponge nutrition. However, few studies have actually demonstrated that sponges containing photosymbionts have positive gross production/respiration (PR) ratios, indicating sponges are primarily reliant on their symbionts for nutrition (but see Wilkinson 1983).

There have been no studies from the Mediterranean, North Eastern Pacific, North Atlantic or from polar regions to measure sponge phototrophy. While photosynthetic sponges might be considered to be a feature of tropical systems, where light penetration is high, photosynthetic symbionts are also found in sponges from temperate bioregions. Roberts et al. (1999) tested the chlorophyll concentration of eight common sponge species from New South Wales in the Temperate Australasian bioregion and found that the majority were heterotrophic. Furthermore, although five species had detectable chlorophyll levels, three had low chlorophyll α concentrations ($<25 \mu\text{g chl g(sponge)}^{-1}$), one species had intermediate chlorophyll α concentrations ($85.3 \mu\text{g chl g(sponge)}^{-1}$), and only *Cymbastela concentrica* had high levels of chlorophyll α ($139.4 \mu\text{g chl g(sponge)}^{-1}$). However, sponges in Southern Western Australia show a different pattern. For example, Lemoh et al. (2009) surveyed shallow (3–8 m) coastal areas and used both PAM fluorometry and fluorescence microscopy to identify the presence of photosynthesis in sponges. The authors identified 63 different sponge species, the majority of which displayed photosynthetic properties. An average of 48% of sponge species (63% of individuals) were 'strongly' photosynthetic and 16% of the species (11% of individuals) had low to medium levels of photosynthetic symbionts. In New Zealand (temperate Australasia bioregion), a recent PAM survey of 62 sponges at the Poor Knights Marine Reserve found only one species with detectable levels of photosynthetic activity (Bell unpublished data).

Sponge assemblages in the Tropical West Atlantic bioregion (particularly the Caribbean) are thought to be largely dominated by heterotrophic species, while those from Tropical Australia (GBR) are thought to be largely dependent on photosymbionts to meet their nutritional requirements. However, this broad assumption is based on the work of Wilkinson (1987), who used spectrophotometric analysis (rather than PR ratio) to assess the presence of photosynthetic sponges on Caribbean reefs (in Barbados, Belize, Florida, Jamaica, Puerto Rico and US Virgin Islands) and compared these to sponges on the GBR. His results showed that across all sites in the Caribbean, heterotrophic sponges were dominant and photosymbiont-containing sponges were almost entirely absent. However, the presence of photosymbionts in sponges does not necessarily mean such sponges are deriving a major portion of their nutrition from these symbionts. For example, Thiel et al. (2007) found cyanobacteria associated with the temperate sponge *Tethya aurantium*, but it seems unlikely they are relying on these symbionts for nutrition, since other temperate *Tethya* species feed extensively heterotrophically (Perea-Blaquez et al. 2012). More recently, Erwin and Thacker (2007) found a higher abundance of photosynthetic sponges on Panamanian reefs. The sponge assemblage on these reefs was found to be divided into two distinct groups: 20 species (33%) had high levels of chlorophyll from photosynthetic symbionts ($> 125 \mu\text{g chl g-sponge-tissue}^{-1}$), but the majority of these sponge species (38 species, 63%) had low levels of chlorophyll ($<50 \mu\text{g chl g(sponge)}^{-1}$). Only two species had intermediate chlorophyll concentrations. However, once again this study did not empirically show the contribution of photosynthetically derived carbon to sponge nutrition. It does however, suggest that the assertion by Wilkinson (1987), that Caribbean reef sponges are predominately heterotrophic, may be misleading.

To date there have been no assessments of the reliance of entire sponge assemblages on photosymbionts in South East Asian bioregion. However, there are reports of species with photosynthetic symbionts. For example, the sponge *Lamellodysidea herbacea* is phototrophic and also shows an ability to photoacclimate (Biggerstaff et al. 2017). In the central Pacific, Freeman and Easson (2016) surveyed a variety of shallow ($< 10 \text{ m}$) marine habitats in Moorea, French Polynesia. While they

found sponge abundance and diversity was very low, accounting for less than 1% of cover and represented by just seven species, the majority of these species were heterotrophic. Five species were restricted to shaded/cryptic habitats and had low ($<50 \mu\text{g chl g}(\text{sponge})^{-1}$) chlorophyll α concentrations, one species (*Haliclona* sp.) had intermediate chlorophyll α concentrations ($50\text{--}125 \mu\text{g chl g}(\text{sponge})^{-1}$) and *Lendenfeldia chondrodes*, which was found in exposed areas, had significantly higher chlorophyll α concentrations ($\sim 300\text{--}675 \mu\text{g chl g}(\text{sponge})^{-1}$). Once again however, the contribution of photosynthetically derived carbon to sponge nutrition has not been demonstrated. Using a different approach, Steindler et al. (2002) investigated the incidence of photosynthesis in intertidal and subtidal sponges around the island of Zanzibar in the Western Indian Ocean bioregion. Sponges were investigated using pulse amplitude modulated (PAM) fluorometry and subsequent chlorophyll content analysis for those sponges that fluoresced. Of the 77 species surveyed in the region, 55 (71.5%) were determined by PAM analysis to be photosynthetically active, with a higher number of these species occurring in intertidal habitats than in the subtidal ($< 12 \text{ m}$). However, the authors did not report the chlorophyll content or P:R ratios for each species; therefore, it is unknown how many of the 55 species are nutritionally reliant upon their photosymbionts.

Several studies on the GBR have characterised sponge assemblages as having a high proportion of phototrophic sponges. Wilkinson (1983) tested the productivity of 10 of the most common sponges on the fore-reef slope of Davies Reef (GBR) and found that 6 of these species were net primary producers. Further work on this reef system (Wilkinson and Trott 1985; Wilkinson 1987; Wilkinson and Cheshire 1990) found large differences in the relative abundance of heterotrophic versus phototrophic sponges with distance from the land. Phototrophic sponges represented over 90% of sponge biomass on some outer reefs, but were absent from sponge assemblages on many turbid inner reefs. On middle-shelf reefs, approximately 40% (by biomass) of sponges were phototrophic, 50% were fully heterotrophic, and another 10% had low levels of photosymbiotic cyanobacteria.

An assumption that high sponge concentrations of chlorophyll equates to high levels of photosynthetically derived nutrition for the sponge host is becoming increasingly common in the literature. However, more work is required to empirically test what proportion of sponge carbon requirements are met from their symbionts in sponges containing high levels of chlorophyll.

Competition

To examine inter-phyletic competition with sponges across bioregions, we conducted searches using the key-words 'sponge/Porifera', and 'competition' and 'interaction'. The search revealed 354 studies. Only papers dealing with competition for space or resources between sponges and other benthic organisms were considered (rather than intra-phyletic competition). Overall, 118 studies considered sponge competition with other organisms. Studies were categorized according to the method used to assess the competition. The methods were categorized as follows: 1) observational studies, including temporal and static observations; 2) manipulative experiments, for studies where competition was assessed through manipulative field experiments monitored over time; 3) laboratory experiments, for studies carried out in mesocosms or in a laboratory under controlled conditions; 4) models, for studies in which the outcome of competitive interactions was inferred using a mathematical model framework; and 5) indirect observations, for studies where competition was not experimentally observed, but the authors discussed possible competitive interactions. For each study, the organism competing with the sponge and the outcome of the competition were considered. In total, 189 interactions between sponges and other organisms were found across these studies.

We used all 118 studies to compare the frequency of sponges encountering different competitors within the bioregions (Figure 15). However, a subset of suitable papers ($n=60$) were used to consider

the outcome of the competition within the bioregions (Figure 16), which only included the studies that inferred competition using temporal data, since this is important for assessing competitive interactions (Chornesky 1989; Wulff 2012). Sponge competition has been most studied in tropical bioregions (69.5% of all studies, n=82), while 20.3% (n=23) of the studies were from temperate bioregions and 6.8% (n=8) from the Mediterranean. Polar bioregions have been far less-studied with only 6 studies, representing 5.1% of the total. Globally, the main sponge competitors were anthozoans, which were reported in 66.9% of the published studies, followed by algae (33.9%), ascidians (16.1%), bryozoans (15.3%), and polychaetes (8.5%). Other sessile invertebrates competing with sponges, reported in less than 10 studies, were molluscs (7.6%), barnacles (5.9%), hydrozoans (3.4%), foraminiferans (1.7%), and brachiopods (0.8%). Although the results of competition with anthozoans, ascidians, and algae were variable between bioregions, sponges nearly always outcompeted all other invertebrates.

In tropical bioregions, anthozoans were the most frequently reported sponge competitors (67.9% of interactions) (Figure 15). Interactions were generally focused on competition between sponges and hermatypic corals (e.g. Hill 1998; Suchanek et al. 1983). However, sponge interactions were strongly influenced by the habitat examined. For instance, in light-exposed environments, sponges mainly compete with corals and algae (Ramsby et al. 2017), while in cryptic coral reef environments, sponges compete with other invertebrates, such as ascidians and bryozoans (Buss and Jackson 1979). After anthozoans, algae were the most frequent sponge competitors, reported in 19 studies (17.4%), followed by sessile invertebrates (14.7%). In the Middle East and South-East Asia bioregions, anthozoans constitute 100% of the reported competitors (although sponges likely compete with other organisms on the reef). In the Indian Ocean and Central Pacific bioregions, anthozoans were also the main competitors with sponges (87.5% and 83.3%, respectively), but in these bioregions, sponges have also been reported to compete with algae. In the Tropical West Atlantic and Tropical Australia bioregions, the main competitors were anthozoans (60.0% and 54.5%, respectively), but there were also high reports of competition with algae (18.6% and 36.4%, respectively) and other sessile invertebrates (21.4% and 9.1%, respectively). No studies were found for the Tropical East Atlantic (based on our criteria).

With respect to the outcome of competition in tropical bioregions, sponges generally appeared to be stronger competitors than anthozoans, being the winners in 63.9% of the reported cases, while in 13.9% of cases they were outcompeted by anthozoans. In 22.2% of the interactions, there was a tied outcome where neither competitor gained space over the other. However, it is likely that these results might be biased because a large number of studies only consider one or few species for each taxon, and often species with fast growth rates and opportunistic strategies (Rützler 2002; Thinesh et al. 2017). Algae, in contrast, have been reported as more competitive in 66.7% of the studies, and less competitive in the remaining studies.

The main sponge competitors in the Mediterranean were algae (45.5% of the interactions), while other sessile invertebrates accounted, together, for the remaining 54.5%. In particular anthozoans and bryozoans, which represented 18.2% each of the competitors, and ascidians and polychaetes accounting for 9.1% each. Only two studies investigated the outcomes of anthozoan-sponge interactions, reporting a tied outcome in both cases. Algae were reported to outcompete sponges in the two papers that investigated interactions between these two organisms.

In temperate bioregions, the main competitors with sponges reported were algae, bryozoans, and ascidians (25.9%; 17.2%; and 15.5%, of the competitive interactions, respectively), while anthozoans

accounted for only 5.2% of interactions. Reports of competition with algae appeared to be particularly common in Temperate Australasia (66.7%), while in the North Atlantic and North Pacific bioregions, algae accounted for only 23.1% and 19.2% of the reported interactions respectively, with invertebrates having more interactions (76.9% and 80.8%, respectively). No studies were found for the South East Pacific and South Atlantic bioregions. For temperate bioregions, habitat is important because in light-exposed conditions sponges mainly compete with algae, while in dim light, other groups including ascidians, bryozoans, and coralline algae, are more important sponge competitors. Outcomes of anthozoan-sponge interactions in temperate bioregions have only reported tied outcomes. Algae in contrast have been reported to be outcompeted by sponges in 60.0% of the interactions, while sponges are outcompeted in 30% of the cases, with only one study reporting a tied sponge-algae outcome.

In the polar seas, sponges mainly compete with invertebrates such as ascidians (30.8%), molluscs (23.1%) and bryozoans (15.4%). Algae, anthozoans, barnacles and hydrozoans have been reported as competitors, but only in one study.

Figure 15. a) The main sponge competitors for tropical, Mediterranean, temperate, and polar macroregions, and b) individual bioregions expressed as percentage of interactions reported in literature reviewed. Numbers across the x-axis represent the numbers of observations between sponges and other organisms found for the given microregion or bioregion.

Figure 16. a) Outcome of competition between sponges and anthozoans, and b) sponges and algae, from tropical, Mediterranean, temperate, and polar macroregions. Numbers across the y-axis represent the total number of studies on which the proportions are based.

Inter-ocean patterns

We found some clear differences between sponge assemblages across the bioregions and macroregions. However, in many cases there were no clear trends, which likely results from the high levels of variability in sponge measurements/observations. This is perhaps not surprising given the relatively low number of observations for some of the variables we considered, and the variation in these traits between different sponge species. However, the 15 different bioregions we have considered will vary considerably with respect to large-scale biotic and abiotic conditions, and particularly with respect to water temperature and productivity/food availability, which would be expected to strongly influence sponges. This may explain some of the stronger consistencies in the

data, with patterns reported likely representing a combination of common ancestry, along with the biological and physical processes that have influenced the evolutionary history of sponges over time.

A number of methods can be used to estimate sponge abundance, including biomass, area occupied and number of patches (see Bell et al. 2016 for review). While biomass and volume have been proposed as the most appropriate methods to estimate sponge abundance by some authors (see Wulff 2001), this is very difficult and impractical for thinly encrusting species (which make up the majority of sponges across the world), and may not always be representative of their functional importance. Therefore, outside the Western Tropical Atlantic it might be more appropriate to estimate sponge abundance with respect to area occupied rather than attempt to characterise biomass or volume. Patterns of sponge abundance (based on density – number of patches and area occupied) were highly variable within the 15 bioregions, and most data were available from the 0–20 m depth range. There was evidence of considerably higher area occupied in the Mediterranean compared to the other bioregions (0–20 m), and higher densities of sponges in temperate bioregions compared with tropical and polar bioregions (noting little data were available for polar regions). From the data that were available from polar bioregions, sponge cover between 20–40 m can be very high (up to 50%), but with low abundance between 0–20 m, presumably because of ice scour effects (Dayton 1989, Dayton et al. 2013). Because of the variability of sponge abundance, cover and species richness within and between bioregions, it was not possible to clearly conclude which bioregions support the most abundant or diverse sponge assemblages. Given the high complexity of sponge assemblages, the variety of drivers that shape them, and the inherent variability of different locations and studies, and times of sampling, this was not surprising. Importantly, numerous studies have described the influence of local-scale environmental factors on sponge abundance and assemblage composition (e.g. Bell and Barnes 2000; Powell et al. 2014, Marlow et al. 2019). Furthermore, sponge assemblages can show strong temporal changes in abundance and biodiversity across many ecosystems. For example, censuses made over 14 years at a permanent site in Panama showed a steady decline of sponge species (53.1%) with time (Wulff, 2006). Furthermore, sponge abundance on an Indonesian coral reef was also found to fluctuate by as much as >60% over a 13-year monitoring period (Rovellini et al. 2019). Temperate sponge assemblages can also show strong seasonal changes (e.g. Berman et al. 2013), and Dayton et al. (2013) reported sudden shifts in biomass of the Antarctic sponge *Anoxycalyx joubini* driven by stochastic environmental events. Therefore, inherent temporal variability also likely contributed to the degree of variability in published values of sponge abundance and diversity. However, collating the available measurements of sponge abundance highlighted that sponges can be very abundant on hard substrates across the world, thus are an important component of these ecosystems worldwide.

We used mean species richness per m² as an estimate of the local-scale concentrations of sponge diversity. We found very similar values across the bioregions where data were available, with the exception of three locations, two temperate (both Atlantic bioregions) and one tropical (South East Asia) bioregion, where much higher concentrations of species were found (between 15–25 species per m²). Given these species are likely to require many of the same resources, particularly substrate availability and food, the evolutionary histories to allow so many species to co-exist in such a small area are likely to be complex and remain unexplored.

Sponges are a morphologically diverse group and to ensure consistency between studies and enable comparisons between the bioregions, we had to aggregate morphologies into major categories. We found generally consistent patterns between all the bioregions, and this consistency persisted at the macroregional level. A general dominance of encrusting sponge morphologies was reported in almost all bioregions, with the notable exception of Tropical West Atlantic where massive and upright forms

were more common. These results were consistent with those of Carballo et al. (2019) who reported more massive sponge forms on Caribbean coral reefs compared to coral reefs in the Eastern and Western Pacific. While our aggregation of the data almost certainly masks much of the morphological diversity within sponges, it does indicate that low profile morphologies are a dominant feature of sponge assemblages globally. This has implications for sponge monitoring, and for the characterisation of sponge assemblages. The contribution of morphologically diverse sponge assemblages to the structural complexity of the seafloor has been studied for some ecosystems, including the deep sea (reviewed in Buhl-Mortensen et al. 2010) and estuarine temperate systems (van Lier et al. 2017), but it remains largely unknown for coral and other shallow reefs. Patterns of dominance of encrusting sponges across the world's oceans suggest that sponges are, on average, a low contributor to overall structural complexity (with the exception of continental shelf and deep-sea sponge beds, which were not considered in this review). However, sponges may function as providers of reef architecture in systems where massive and upright growth forms are common (e.g. the Tropical West Atlantic). Further research is needed to elucidate this functional role of sponges, and its importance in different bioregions (see Bell et al. 2018 for further discussion).

Our analysis of sponge reproduction found some consistent patterns, but again also considerable variability with regards to the metrics we considered. There were no patterns in gametic development (hermaphroditism versus gonochorism), while temperate, tropical and polar macroregions contained an increasing percentage of viviparous species, with viviparity being the sole mechanism for gamete development reported for polar sponges. As expected, reproductive timing was generally seasonal in temperate regions and continuous in the tropical bioregions, likely representing differences in the seasonality of food supply in temperate bioregions and temperate-associated development (see Cebrián & Valiela 1999). We found that the dominant larval type was parenchymella, which may be ancestral to all Demospongiae (Wörheide et al. 2012), and hence explains its dominance across sponge species. Asexual reproduction, despite being considered an important feature of sponges, especially since most sponges can be easily split into clones, has not been widely reported as a reproductive strategy. Data were only available for four bioregions (Mediterranean, Temperate Australasia, Tropical Australia and Tropical West Atlantic), which is likely because it is an understudied topic. It is highly probable that asexual reproduction is not limited to just these bioregions. The lack of reports of asexual reproduction does not necessarily mean asexual reproduction is absent or insignificant for sponges. For instance, reliance on asexual reproduction appears to vary between sponges, where some rely more heavily on asexual reproduction for population maintenance (Wulff 1991; Shaffer 2019); but for others, asexual reproduction does not appear to frequently occur or play an important role in structuring populations (Blanquer and Uriz 2010).

Surprisingly, across all 15 bioregions we found no strong patterns in the key physiological processes of respiration and pumping rate, although there was some evidence for reduced respiration rates for polar sponges (but based on a small number of observations). Instead, we observed high levels of variability in the data. Sponge respiration in particular is known to be strongly influenced by temperature, with increased respiration reported in many experimental studies examining thermal effects (e.g. Bennett et al. 2018; and see Bell et al. 2018). However, we considered only 'control' respiration rates from experimental studies, in order to provide the most accurate estimates of 'natural' respiration rates, as few studies have attempted to measure respiration rates under completely natural conditions (but see Reiswig 1974; Coma et al. 2002; Yahel 2003; Ludeman et al. 2017). Consistent with the results from respiration rates, we also found no clear trends for pumping rates. There have been a number of estimates of the energetic cost of pumping with estimates ranging

between 1 and 25% of total sponge energy use (see Hadas et al. 2008; Ludeman et al. 2017). This variation in estimates is likely the result of differences in sponge-specific features, such as internal sponge morphological structure and actual pumping rates, along with abiotic factors like temperature, which influence water viscosity and enzymatic processes (Ludeman et al. 2017). If pumping represents a considerable energetic cost for some species and not for others, this is also likely to contribute to the high variability in both pumping and respiration rates. We also found only weak evidence for a pattern in sponge growth. However, it is important to note that the metric we chose to compare, which was based on the largest database of available information, was based on percentage increase in size (relative increase), and not on some measure of actual biomass increase overtime. We found similar patterns of relative growth across all macroregions, with a potential difference between tropical bioregions compared to temperate and polar regions.

There is a considerable amount of prior research on sponge predation, which appears more important in controlling sponge assemblage population dynamics in tropical and polar regions compared to temperate regions, although the diversity of sponge predators is also much higher in the tropics (Wulff 2006). The overall importance of top-down versus bottom-up processes in controlling sponge abundance and assemblage composition has received considerable debate (reviewed in Pawlik et al. 2018), although this previous work has been focused predominantly on tropical environments from the Tropical Western Atlantic bioregion, while in the other tropical bioregions predation appears less important as a controlling mechanism (see Powell et al. 2015). It is unclear why sponge predators are not more abundant or important in temperate bioregions, especially fish predators, but these might include differences in nutritional value, higher diversity of available food resources, less diversification of predators, and differences in chemical defence abilities between sponges. It has been shown in earlier studies that chemical defences from tropical and temperate sponges are equally effective against predators, suggesting recurrent selection for chemical defences in sponges as a general life-history strategy (Becerro et al. 2003). Therefore, chemical defences alone cannot explain differences in the relative importance of predators between tropical and temperate environments and other factors must be important.

There is limited evidence of any true phototrophic sponges (i.e. sponges hosting photosymbionts and using their photosynthesis products for nutrition) in temperate or polar regions. However, this does not mean sponges from these regions do not contain photosynthetic symbionts, just that they are unlikely to play a major role in sponge nutrition (but may have other roles; see Webster and Taylor 2012). There is a general perception from the limited literature available that there is a higher proportion of phototrophic species in the Indo-Pacific bioregions compared to the Tropical Western Atlantic bioregion, and that these phototrophic species are more reliant on photosynthetically derived carbon than from heterotrophic feeding (see above). This has been explained by the better water quality (and presumably lower turbidity) in the Indo-Pacific region (Wilkinson 1987). However, the Indo-Pacific region has a much greater diversity of sponges compared to the Western Tropical Atlantic, and the actual number of species that are phototrophic may be small compared to heterotrophic species, meaning the overall contribution of phototrophic sponges to reef function could be smaller than currently thought. Given the perception in the literature regarding heterotrophy versus autotrophy, and the implications this may have for the role sponges play on Indo-Pacific reefs, there is a need to conduct a more systematic investigation of the level of sponge heterotrophy versus autotrophy on coral reefs.

Finally, sponges are well-known strong spatial competitors in benthic environments (Jackson and Buss 1975; Vicente 1990; Bell and Barnes 2003; Wulff 2006), and generally outcompete all other invertebrates for space, but do often get outcompeted by algae and corals, irrespective of bioregions.

Interestingly, while sponges are often top spatial competitors, there is often large amounts (10-50%) of bare space on temperate and polar rocky substrates, suggesting competitive interactions are not ultimately important in controlling sponge abundance in these bioregions. For tropical macroregions, however, since there are more reports of sponges showing competitive dominance over scleractinian corals than vice versa, other factors must limit the ability of sponges to gain space from corals. Alternatively, the studies available on sponge-coral interactions might not be representative of all sponge-coral interactions. Our results here support Pawlik and McMurray (2019) who, at least for the Caribbean, consider sponges to have more negative effects on corals than positive ones (but see Wulff 2017 for an alternative view).

Conclusion

While our analyses do demonstrate some clear differences between some bioregions, there are also many similarities in sponge assemblage structure and function at global scales. These patterns are likely driven by a combination of common ancestry, evolutionary history, and regional and local scale biological and physical processes. We hope this review will enable researchers working in different biogeographic regions to get a better overview of how sponges function in other bioregions and give context to interpret future findings in the areas of study we have considered.

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